

MESHFREE METHODS FOR PHYSICS-BASED CRACK MODELING

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SUMMARY

The Finite Element Method (FE) is the analytical workhorse for structural and solid mechanics. As applied to systems with evolving topologies, such as crack initiation and propagation, or fracture in anisotropic media, such as laminated composites, FE has limitations. We present a new method for analysis of laminated composites that address these limitations.

Keywords: Meshfree, crack morphology, GSC model, physics-based modeling

INTRODUCTION

Physical phenomena in some important areas, such as fracture, fundamentally occur in a discontinuous fashion. On the other hand, most methods for solving structural mechanics problems, e.g. the finite element method, are formulated to solve for continuous field variables. To model a crack in a continuum model requires embedding some model of discontinuity into the continuous formulation. Numerous approaches using this methodology have been introduced, such as X-FEM, cohesive cracks, element erosion, etc. These methods have achieved some degree of success. Purely discrete models, such as molecular dynamics (MD), can naturally evolve to open up discontinuities in a material. However, the number of molecules required for MD simulations capable of modeling practical engineering fracture problems is prohibitively large. Thus, there seems to be a place for a simple method to solve the continuum equations, but easily incorporate discontinuities. For laminated composites, the fiber orientation has a profound effect on how cracks can propagate. In mesh-based analysis methods based, the mesh orientation may influence the crack direction, but it may conflict with the physical requirements dictated by the fiber orientation. This paper presents a method based on one of the so-called meshfree methods, in this case the Reproducing Kernel Particle Method (RKPM). The method explicitly models cracks and changing topology and is formulated to reduce or eliminate discretization choices from influencing the solution. Further, the model naturally provides a mechanism for

incorporating information that is not contained in the governing continuum equations to determine crack initiation and direction. We demonstrate how this can be combined with an external model to realistically simulate fracture in engineering analysis of laminated composites. In some sense, this latter property may be viewed a sort of multi-scale model.

CRACK MORPHOLOGY

The Reproducing Kernel Particle Method was first introduced in [1] and provides a method to construct a function basis for use in Galerkin solutions to partial differential equations without using a mesh, but rather through locally and perhaps dynamically determined interactions between nodes. Since a mesh is not required to form the function space, it can evolve dynamically, and in particular, can be adjusted as the material topology changes. The RKPM method constructs a local interpolation field centered at each node that is based on local interaction with neighboring nodes. By introducing a visibility condition during a calculation, one can selectively limit the interaction between nodes to effectively cut the material.

A crack morphology and propagation algorithm that conserves mass and energy was developed for two-dimensions in [2]. This algorithm was extended to three-dimensional through-cracks of directed surfaces. This is ideal for use in thin walled structures such as pressure cylinders and aircraft hulls. The crack is restricted to move only between particles and the interpolation field can be dynamically altered by changes in particle topology due to this cracking by use of a visibility criterion. The node splitting algorithm uses information determined from the constitutive model to determine when a node should be split. Based upon this damage measure the crack propagation algorithm automatically chooses crack direction and propagation. The ability to couple node splitting to a damage measure is immensely powerful. In fact, it can be viewed as a link between the structural mechanics equations and an externally (to the mechanics equations) determined quantity. There is no need for the external quantity to be continuous and its insertion into the simulation is done for each node, and is thus discontinuous. Proper selection of the external damage measure allows a researcher to incorporate information from knowledge bases, or detailed physics-based multi-scale calculations. An example of the three-dimensional algorithm applied to a pressurized cylinder with localized heating using the Johnson-Cook model with damage estimate is shown in Fig. 1. The black dots represent nodes, the color contours are of the external damage.

Figure 1: Crack propagation

SUB-SCALE MODELING FOR COMPOSITES

The standard method of modeling composites is the continuum approach where the effects of the composite fibers are idealized as material properties of a continuum model. This, in a sense, is a form of the multi-scale problem. The fibers themselves are too small to be modeled explicitly and so this information is included in the model in the form of material properties. Even if the small scale of the fibers could be represented, the actual location of these in the matrix is knowledge that is difficult if not impossible to obtain with any reliable amount of certainty. The continuum approach works well for applications provided that the composite material properties are accurately determined.

When failure is to be modeled, especially cracking, the information lost in the idealization of the fibers becomes critical. Cracking models based on continua will not predict the correct crack morphology due to the absence of actual fibers. This paper discusses a method developed that returns physical knowledge to the model without the need to explicitly model fibers in the composite. This enables the straightforward use of continuum mechanics to solve crack propagation problems in laminated fibrous composites which will model the physical behavior.

While the cracking algorithm described in the previous section will function with any failure discriminator, in this case we base failure on the Boeing emergent failure theory, described elsewhere. Here, a unique discriminator is described which reflects failure in the matrix due to distortional strain and failure in the fiber due to shear strain.

The idealization of the fibers as material properties comes at the cost of accuracy. For added accuracy, prior to the calculation of material utilization, the states of strain are micro-mechanically enhanced using information from more detailed models. While the modeling of composites as continua is convenient, there are residual strains induced by the fiber-matrix interface not captured by the continuum model. This enhancement technique corrects the strains, adding more physics to the approximated solution.

The particle splitting algorithm used to model the crack propagation also suffers from the lack of explicitly modeled fibers. The morphology is only guided by the measure of material utilization, however, there are crack trajectories generated by this algorithm that are unphysical. This paper is concerned with detailing a method for restoring lost information to the propagation algorithm. The imposition of physics into the referenced cracking algorithm is what we call the Gosse-Simkins-Collier (GSC) model and is described in more detail in the following section.

The GSC Model

The GSC model can be generalized as a list of criteria that limits the possible locations

Figure 2: Schematic of composite showing fibers in grey and matrix in white. The 0° case (left) shows a restricted crack morphology. The 90° case (right) is permitted as no fibers are severed.

to which a crack may propagate. First we restrict the cracking to be in the orientation of the fibers. Cracking against the fiber orientation requires that the fibers fail, which typically does not occur under normal loading. This situation can be seen in Fig. 2. On the left the fibers are oriented from left to right and the crack passes through them. This kind of morphology is restricted because it is unphysical. On the right the fibers are oriented into the page and the crack shown in the matrix only.

In a multi-layer composite, cracking does not propagate from one lamina to another. Instead, delamination occurs when the crack reaches the interface. This is handled by

limiting the meshfree particles to which a crack may propagate. Consider Fig. 3 where a portion of a $0^0/90^0/0^0$ layup is shown. The 0^0 plies are shaded and the fibers oriented left to right. The 90^0 ply is white and its fibers are aligned coming in and out of the page. The small circles drawn represent the distribution of meshfree particles.

Figure 3: Details of the GSC model as they apply to multi-laminate composites

In this example, a crack has initiated at a particle labeled A. The crack is shown by the dark, solid line connected to particle A. The crack is free to propagate in the lamina until it reaches the interface, represented here by a particle B. The normal cracking algorithm allows propagation to any neighboring particle in front of particle B. In this case these candidate particles are indicated by a region defined by a dashed line. However, if at a lamina interface, the propagation cannot move into the next lamina, nor return into the original lamina. Once a crack reaches this interface, the crack may only propagate in such a way as to cause delamination. This is consistent with what is physically seen in experiments.

When cracks initiate inside a lamina, a criteria also governs the subset of particles to which cracks may propagate. Consider a particle labeled C again in Fig. 3 which represents the initiation of a crack. To determine candidate propagation particles, we use the following procedure.

1. Extract the state of strain in the plane normal to the fiber direction from the total strain tensor. For the 90^0 ply in Fig. 3 this corresponds to the state of strain in the plane corresponding to that of the page.
2. Determine the maximum principle strain (ϵ_{max}) and accompanying direction. In Fig. 3 this direction is depicted as a vector originating at particle C and labeled, ϵ_{max} . This is observed to be the direction in which cracks open in the laminates.
3. The crack propagation direction is perpendicular to the maximum principle strain. Due to coarse granularity of the particle distribution, it is unlikely that a particle to which a crack may propagate exists in this direction. Candidate particles are chosen to lie within the 45^0 cone around this direction as well as in

the current layer of the lamina. These particles are shown with light shading in Fig. 3.

These candidate particles are determined as a crack initiates, and maintained as it propagates. As the crack propagates and searches for new crack directions, particles which are not in the candidate subset determined when the crack initiated are ignored.

RESULTS

The efficacy of the GSC method was tested on the following beam problem subjected to bending. The schematic for this problem can be seen in Fig. 4. There are five lamina shown in a 0/90/0/90/0 configuration. This beam was represented by a collection of particles in three-dimensional space shown in Fig. 5. The RKPM basis functions used reproduce a tri-linear polynomial field and the window function selected was the radial-based conical function. Integration of the domain was accomplished by the 2x2x2 Gauss quadrature rule using a hexagonal background mesh whose mesh nodes are coincident with the domain particles (3600 integration cells).

Figure 4: Schematic of the three-point bending problem

Figure 5: Particle distribution for beam problem (5733 particles), with three particles through the thickness.

Each lamina used was of the same material whose properties are summarized in Table 1. Note the thermal properties provided. A temperature difference is included which represents the difference between manufacture temperature and room temperature. Since the laminae possess different thermal expansions in the parallel and orthogonal

fiber direction, there are thermal strains that are present before loading occurs. These thermal strains were included in the simulation and computed as part of the initial state.

Table 1: Material property values for beam problem. E, ν , G, and α refers to elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, shear modulus, and thermal expansion coefficient, respectively. The subscripts 1,2, and 3 refer to the local orientation of the laminate where the 1 direction coincides with the fiber orientation.

Quantity	Value	Quantity	Value
Length (m)	2.540e-1	G_{12} (Pa)	4.137e9
Thickness (m)	1.270e-2	G_{13} (Pa)	4.137e9
Height (m)	5.080e-2	G_{23} (Pa)	3.329e9
E_1 (Pa)	1.379e11	α_1 (K^{-1})	0.000e0
E_2 (Pa)	9.653e9	α_2 (K^{-1})	1.111e-5
E_3 (Pa)	9.653e9	α_3 (K^{-1})	1.111e-5
ν_1	3.300e-1	ΔT (K)	-1.694e2
ν_2	3.300e-1		
ν_3	4.500e-1		

Figure 6: Material utilization based on dilatational strain

In Fig. 6 an enlarged, central section of the beam is shown with values of the dilatation strain based material utilization shown interpolated between particles. The blue rectangles shown represent cracks that have started and begun to propagate. Note that these cracks have initiated in the 90^0 ply and are oriented in a manner consistent with the loading of the beam. The cracks nearest the center on both sides have initiated within the lamina and in two cases have begun to cause delamination.

Another classic problem was solved as a test. A single lamina fibrous composite plate was modeled with a hole in it. This plate can be seen in Fig. 7 subjected to a tensile load. The fiber direction is vertical in this image. The composite material properties were those of the previous analysis. The results of this analysis can be seen in Fig. 8. Note the vertical cracks forming which initiate at the hole. This is consistent with experimental data.

Figure 7: Particle distribution for plate with hole

Figure 8: Emergent cracks parallel to fiber direction

CONCLUSION

The combination of the RKPM crack morphology and propagation algorithm coupled with the GSC model was successful in producing an analysis which correctly predicted the location and propagation of failure without the use of pre-knowledge where failure should occur. To accomplish this, a linear-elastic model was used with strain-based discriminators of failure. The states of strain were micro-mechanically enhanced to correct for the residual matrix-fiber strains present. Finally the meshfree crack propagation algorithm was enhanced with physical knowledge, the result of which is a high fidelity solution.

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